

Effect of prevailing temperature and humidity on rice armyworm reproduction during upland crop season

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Rice armyworm *Mythimna loreyi* (Dup.) migrates from rice to other cereal crops in areas where multiple cropping is the practice and climatic variations are extreme. In North India, it attacks rice Jun-Nov, then migrates to wheat, barley, sugarcane, oat, and napier Dec-May.

To study the effect of prevailing Dec-May temperature and humidity on its reproductive biology, we used adults from the mass culture raised in the

laboratory at 26±1 °C in BOD incubators. Each month, 15 freshly emerged pairs (male + female) were released separately in glass jars (15 × 10 cm) with muslin cloth covers. Dry sugarcane leaves kept in jars for egg laying were renewed daily after initiation of oviposition. A sucrose solution (10%)-soaked cotton swab provided for feeding.

Females always survived longer (4.5-21.2 d) than males (4.0-11.0 d) (see table). In spite of a longer oviposition period (10-11 d) during Dec-Jan, females laid fewer eggs (75-95 eggs/female) and more infertile ones because of low temperature. Rising temperatures (9-26 °C) in Feb enhanced fecundity and hatching. During Mar (12-32 °C) and Apr (18-36 °C),

temperature considerably reduced the oviposition period (4-5 d) compared to Dec-Jan (10-11 d) but increased fecundity about 3 times, with 29.4-42.4% hatching. Average daily egg output was also higher during Feb-Apr than during Dec-Jan. In May, high temperature (24-42 °C) significantly reduced adult longevity and fecundity. Eggs laid in May did not hatch.

In December and March relative humidity was almost the same, indicating its insignificant role. During the experimental period, however, optimum conditions (25-30 °C and 75-85% RH) never prevailed, resulting in poor overall fecundity and egg viability. It appears that rice armyworm reproduction is most affected by temperature. □

Effect of prevailing temperature and humidity on reproductive activity of rice armyworm adults.^a Hisar, India.

Month	Temperature (°C)		Relative humidity (%)	Pre-oviposition period (d)	Oviposition period (d)	Postoviposition period (d)	Adult longevity (d)		Eggs (no./female)	Eggs (no./d)	Incubation period (d)	Hatching (%)
	Max	Min					Male	Female				
Dec	18±2.3	8±1.5	59±5.2	10.0	10.0	1.0	10.0	21.0	75	7.5	—	—
Jan	20±2.1	6±2.4	70±4.5	9.8	11.0	0.5	9.0	21.2	95	8.6	—	—
Feb	26±2.8	9±3.0	57±4.0	6.5	5.5	1.2	11.0	13.0	320	58.2	7.5	22.6
Mar	32±2.9	12±3.0	57±3.5	5.0	5.0	2.0	8.0	12.0	253	50.6	5.0	42.4
Apr	36±2.0	18±2.4	45±2.8	3.0	4.0	1.0	5.5	8.0	276	69.0	4.6	29.4
May	42±4.0	24±3.0	36±3.0	3.0	1.0	0.5	4.0	4.5	15	15.0	—	—
LSD (0.05)				2.4	1.6	0.6	2.3	3.4	56	13.5	1.3	10.6

^aAv of 15 replications, 1 pair (female + male) of adults/replication.

Chemical control of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* has become a major pest in both dry and wet season rice in western Orissa. Peak activity during booting causes high yield loss.

We evaluated seven insecticides for WBPH control in the field, in a randomized block design with three replications. Jaya seedlings (35 d old) were transplanted 9 Feb 1987 at 15- × 20-cm spacing in 20-m² plots.

Effect of some insecticides on WBPH population in summer rice. Sambalpur, Orissa, India, 1987.

Insecticide ^a	Formulation	Dose (kg ai/ha)	WBPH population/hill ^b		Grain yield (t/ha)
			69 DT	74 DT	
Chlorpyrifos	10 G	1.0	96.6	48.5	5.1
Ethoprofos	10 G	1.5	137.1	44.8	5.9
Cartap	4 G	1.5	19.3	5.2	6.4
Carbofuran	3 G	1.0	2.5	1.9	6.8
Chlorpyrifos	40 EC	0.5	89.1	11.6	5.3
Decamethrin + buprofezin	5.9 EC	0.09	29.1	7.4	5.6
Phosalone	35 EC	0.5	65.5	33.1	5.3
No insecticide	—	—	109.3	97.3	5.0
LSD (0.05)			48.8	21.7	0.4

^aApplied at 20 and 70 DT. ^bMean of 10 hills.

Insecticides were applied 20 and 70 d after transplanting (DT).

Except for WBPH, no other pests appeared in appreciable numbers. WBPH population was counted at peak

activity and 1 d before and 3 d after the second insecticide application.

At 69 DT, as many as 109 WBPH/ hill were counted in check plots (see table). Carbofuran-treated plots had

the lowest population; cartap and decamethrin + buprofezin had moderate populations. Ethoprofos granules applied 20 DT did not restrict WBPH multiplication at booting; populations on that plot were higher than in the control.

Insecticides applied 70 DT significantly reduced WBPH populations. Carbofuran (1.0 kg ai/ ha) and cartap (1.5 kg ai/ha) were most effective, followed by decamethrin + buprofezin (0.09 kg ai/ha) and chlorpyrifos (0.5 kg ai/ha) spray. □

Residues of monocrotophos in rice

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We studied residues of monocrotophos (3-[dimethoxy phosphinyl oxy]- N -methyl-cis-crotonamide), a common pesticide, in rice variety Lalat (ORS26-2014). The pesticide was sprayed at the recommended level (0.05%, or 0.25 kg ai/ ha) and double the recommended level (0.1%, or 0.50 kg ai/ ha). Triplicate plant samples were collected at 0, 10, 20, and 30 d after spraying and at harvest.

The spectrophotometric method was used to estimate residues of monocrotophos, using p-nitrobenzyl pyridine as the chromogenic reagent. Recovery of monocrotophos from fortified samples was 83.2-84.5%.

Mean initial residues of 10.97 ppm (0.05%) and 19.91 ppm (0.01%) were reduced to 3.26 and 5.19 ppm 10 d after pesticide application, to 1.14 and 2.11 ppm 20 d after application, and to nondetectable levels 30 d after application. Dissipation was 89.5% for both application levels 20 d after application.

Rate of degradation with both application levels seemed to follow the first-order reaction (see figure). Fifty percent of the toxicant was reduced at

Linear plot of first-order reaction of monocrotophos in rice. Bhubaneswar, India.

2.4 d at 0.05% application level and at 2.3 d at 0.1%. The safe waiting period (T_{tol}) was 17.8 d and 19 d.

Grain and straw samples had nondetectable levels of monocrotophos. □

Preliminary observations on *Entomophthora delphacis*

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The pathogen *E. delphacis* of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* is an important entomogenous fungus widely distributed in irrigated ricefields of South China. It attacks mainly BPH, whitebacked planthopper, and small brown planthopper. It also infects zigzag striped leafhopper and green leafhopper (GLH).

E. delphacis usually are most abundant during the overcast and rainy season. In later growth stages of long-duration rice. Infection percentages reach 70-80% when temperatures are 10-

20 °C (day-night) with relative humidity more than 90%. In the Changsha region, the numbers of BPH infected by *E. delphacis* ranged from 37% to 64%. In 1985, a year of high humidity, infection reached 69.7%. In 1986, a dry year, infection was only 27.3%.

We used a fungus suspension on artificial media and naturally infected insects for bioassay to determine virulence on BPH and GLH in the laboratory. Results are presented in the table. Mortality of naturally infected insects was higher than that of artificially infected insects. □

Virulence of *E. delphacis* in the laboratory. Changsha, China.

Pathogen source	Insect tested	Insects (no.)	Mortality (%) after infection		
			2 d	4 d	6 d
Natural	BPH	139	22.8	53.3	68.3
	GLH	92	18.0	32.4	61.1
Artificial ^a	BPH	120	6.3	18.4	31.2
	GLH	120	2.7	11.3	24.3
Control (water)	BPH	110	1.8	1.8	2.7
	GLH	73	2.7	2.7	2.7

^a Sabouraud's agar + egg yolk.

Toya spp. planthopper incidence on *Brachiaria mutica*

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Brachiaria mutica, cultivated in about 15 ha at the Annamalai University Sewage Farm, exhibited severe hopperburn symptoms in Feb 1986 and again in Oct. Investigations revealed abundant numbers of a planthopper.

The delphacid resembles brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, except that it is smaller. Both brachypterous and macropterous forms were seen in large numbers Oct-Dec 1986: smaller numbers are seen throughout the year.